

Supplementary Material

A Hybrid Deep Learning Model CNN-GRU for Crop Yield Prediction Under Climate Impacts: A Case Study of Rice Yield Prediction in India

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Section 0: The selection of the models

The Global Climate Models can be riddled with modelling errors, metadata uncertainty and difficulty in climate prediction. Therefore, it is very important to select an appropriate model as the objective demands.

MIROC6 and NorESM-MM were the CMIP6 models utilised in the study. The decision was made by reviewing the previous literature such as stated by Lee and Wang 2014, Wang et al., 2014 and Sharmila et al., 2014 and a recent paper Patel et al., 2025 to name the few.

Sharmila et al., 2014 studied the interannual variation in Indian Summer Monsoon (ISM) under different CMIP models and found that MIROC5, MPI-ESM-LR, HadGEM2-ES, ACCESS1-0, NorESM1-M perform better than others. Out of 20 models evaluated only BNU-ESM, MPI-ESM-LR, MIROC5 and NorESM1-M were able to simulate the spatial pattern of the intraseasonal variance over ISM region thereby reproducing some of the salient features of the ISM. Lee and Wang 2014 and Wang et al., 2014 show that NorESM1-M and MIROC5 have a good score in simulating a mean state of global and Asian-Australian monsoon.

Patel et al., 2025 studied the performance of 22 GCMs of CMIP6 to conclude the ideal model for daily maximum temperature in East India. The models were evaluated against the data provided by Indian Meteorological Department (IMD) for the period 1951-2014 and concluded that MIROC-ES2L is the best performing model.

As verified by previous studies, MIROC has consistently been one of the best performing model for temperature and ISM accompanied by NorESM-MM.

S. Sharmila, S. Joseph, A.K. Sahai, S. Abhilash, R. Chattopadhyay, Future projection of Indian summer monsoon variability under climate change scenario: An assessment from CMIP5 climate models, *Global and Planetary Change*, Volume 124, 2015, Pages 62-78, ISSN 0921-8181, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloplacha.2014.11.004>.

Patel, G., Das, S. Multi-temporal evaluation of CMIP6 models for maximum temperature in East India: improving climate dynamics understanding. *Stoch Environ Res Risk Assess* (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00477-025-02963-9>

Section 1: Composite Analysis of SST, Precipitation, Temperature, and Vegetation Responses to ENSO and IOD Phases

Figure S1. Composite analysis of sea SST, precipitation, maximum temperature, and Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) for different phases of ENSO and IOD. The SST data is obtained from OISST, precipitation and temperature from IMD, and NDVI from GIMMS.

The above composite maps use observational data of precipitation, maximum temperature, and NDVI during different phases of ENSO and IOD. These validate the literature reviewed in the process of designing and developing the model. As observed, an increase in vegetation is observed La Niña and negative phase of Indian Ocean Dipole (IOD) which also corresponds to the spatial distribution of rainfall and temperature in those respective years. Contrary is observed during El Niño and positive phase of IOD.

Section 2: Statistical Analysis

Figure S2. Pearson's correlations between anomalies of the variables from 1951 to 2011 (1901 - 1950 as reference period).

Figure S3. Scattered pair plots with regression line between anomalies of the variables from 1951 to 2011 (1901 - 1950 as reference period).

The correlation and regression analysis (see figures S2, S3) indicate that rice yield is highly correlated with relative humidity, soil moisture, and Niño 3.4, yet surprisingly, it shows no significant correlation with precipitation and temperature. This suggests that while precipitation does not directly influence rice yield, its impact is mediated through soil moisture and humidity, which are strongly correlated with it. As expected, the precipitation pattern over India is influenced by ENSO and IOD, and a strong

positive correlation is observed between the DMI and precipitation. However, the absence of a clear correlation between ENSO and precipitation is unexpected. These discrepancies may arise from model limitations, raising concerns about whether the chosen rice yield model and CMIP6 climate models sufficiently capture these complex relationships.

Section 3: Spatial climatic variables under different SSP scenarios

Figure S4 (A-D) represent the spatial climatic variables over the Indian subcontinent. Figures E and F represent the ocean input variables.

Figure S4 (A to F) showcases the change in the variables in terms of Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP). Excluding Figure F, all others showcase an expected pattern as SSP 8.5 is a more extreme scenario regarding carbon emissions than SSP 4.5. Figure F shows that a surprisingly intense

variation is DMI under the SSP 245 scenario than the SSP 585. Figure D highlights the absence of soil moisture data for the SSP 245 scenario.

Section 4: Rice yield prediction

Figure S5 - (a) Predicted rice crop yields using input variables from test data. (b) Observed rice crop yields over test data. (c) Percentage difference between predicted and observed values.

Figure S6 - (a) Mean of rice SSP 245 crop yield (2015 - 2100). (b) Mean of rice historical crop yield (1901 - 2011). (c) Differences between future projection and historical data.

Figures S5 and S6 consist of results acquired from the model described in the main text. In Figure S5, there is a noticeable overestimation in the central and Northeast regions of the subcontinent. Figure S6 highlights the change according to the SSP 245 scenario and concludes a noticeable fall in rice yield in the subcontinent.